

CLARIN in University Curricula Workshop

Utrecht, 21 - 22 April 2026

Day 1

13:00 - 17:30

Programme Day 1 / Part 1

- **11:45 - 13:00** Registrations & Welcome Lunch
- **13:00 - 13:15** CLARIN in the Broader Landscape by Darja Fišer
- **13:15 - 13:45** Keynote: What is a Curriculum, really? by Vesna Lušicky
- **13:45 - 14:00** Teaching with CLARIN: Where we were?What has been built?What still needs to happen? by Julianna van der Lek
- **14:00 - 15:00** Lightning Talks: Strategies for Integrating CLARIN into University Curricula
- **15:00 - 15:30 Coffee Break**

CLARIN in the Broader Landscape

Darja Fišer

CLARIN ERIC

SSHOC landscape from the ESFRI perspective: LINKING DATA AND RESEARCHERS ACROSS COUNTRIES AND TIME

SSHOC Strategy and Annual Plans, building on the existing SSHOC MoU

Strategic Pillars to guide the priorities for 2024-2028

Data, Tools and Workflows

- Operate, maintain and further develop the **SSH Open Marketplace**
- Exploring SSHOC's readiness to become a **thematic node** for the Social Sciences and Humanities as part of the EOSC Federation

Training and Education

- Develop a new SSHOC website including a section for the SSH Competence Centre: <https://sshopencloud.eu/ssh-competence-centre>
- Further refine SSHOC Competence Centre activities and develop Competence Centre Action Plan

Advocacy and Outreach

- Represent SSHOC in stakeholder bodies (such as ESFRI, ERIC Forum, Science Clusters, EOSC Association, etc.)

Social Sciences and Humanities Open Marketplace

Tools & services Training materials Publications Datasets Workflows Browse Co

Social Sciences & Humanities Open Marketplace

Discover new and contextualised resources for your research in Social Sciences and Humanities: tools, services, training materials, workflows and datasets. [Read more...](#)

3 Guiding Principles

- Contextualisation
- Curation
- Community

Barbot, L., Dolinar, M., Gray, E. J., Grisot, C., Illmayer, K., Kurzmeier, M., McGillivray, B. (2024). Contextualizing Research Tools & Services Through Workflows in the SSH Open Marketplace. *Journal of Open Humanities Data*, 10 (1), 22. <https://doi.org/10.5334/johd.192>

SSH Competence Centre

The screenshot shows the homepage of the SSH Competence Centre. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the SSHOC logo and links for 'About SSHOC', 'Marketplace', 'Training', 'Data Catalogues', 'SSHOC In Action', 'Resources', and 'News & Events'. A 'Sign in' button is also present. Below the navigation bar, the main heading reads 'SSH Competence Centre - operated by the SSH Open Cluster (SSHOC)'. A sub-heading indicates the page is the 'Home / SSH Competence Centre - operated by the SSH Open Cluster (SSHOC)'. The main content area is divided into two columns. The left column contains a paragraph describing the SSH Competence Centre (SSH CC) as a community-based virtual hub for research excellence in SSH, followed by a list of four competences: 1. Connecting SSH research communities to digital infrastructures, 2. Training and capacity building, 3. Producing and sharing guidelines and best practices, and 4. SSH community engagement and technical support. Below this is a paragraph about the SSH Open Cluster member organizations and a 'Contact us!' button. The right column features a 'News' section with three articles: 'Science Clusters Position statement on operational commitment to EOSC and Open Research', 'SSHOC, the SSH Open Science Cluster has a New Chair and Vice-Chair in 2024', and 'OSCARS project funded to foster the uptake of Open Science in Europe'. Each news item includes a short introductory text.

Aim

Share knowledge and skills among diverse SSH communities supporting open data, interoperability and cross-domain collaboration

Priorities

- Supporting the needs of a range of different audiences
- Strengthening of the SSH Open Marketplace
- Explore AI potential for SSH
- Sustainability and long-term commitment by the ERICs

<https://sshopencloud.eu/ssh-competence-centre>

What Is a Curriculum, Really?

Aligning Curriculum Realities with CLARIN Integration

Vesna Lušicky
University of Vienna

13:15 - 13:45

My connection to CLARIN

- K-Centre for Terminology Resources and Translation Corpora
- Knowledge Infrastructure Committee
- Trainer in CLARIN Trainers' Network

Degree programmes at the Centre for Translation Studies, University of Vienna

BA Transcultural Communication

- 797 students
- 12 languages

MA Translation

- 676 students
- 14 languages
 - Specialised Translation and Language Industry
 - Conference Interpreting
 - Dialogue Interpreting
 - Translation in the Fields of Literature, Audiovisual Media, and the Arts

MSc Multilingual Technologies

- 46 students
- English + 1

What I'll try to address

1. What do we mean by *curriculum*?
2. Why do digital skills, data literacy and research infrastructures often feel like 'add-ons' in teaching?
3. When integration fails: What exactly is the issue?

Why curricula matter

- Higher education institutions face shifting **political, technological, and societal pressures.**
- Language-related disciplines sit at the crossroads of:
 - rapid technological innovation,
 - labour-market expectations and future projections,
 - and the academic mission.

Curriculum: What's in a name?

- “Planned course of learning”

(Taba 1962)

Curriculum: What's in a name?

- Not just *content*, but also:
 - intentions (why),
 - content (what),
 - methods (how),
 - learning outcomes (with what effects),
 - assessment (how well).

(Based on Saywer et al. 2019)

Why is it so hard to ‘just add’ to a curriculum?

- Misalignments:
 - Curriculum as a *neutral container* for content.
 - Curriculum is reduced to syllabi or learning outcomes.
- Integration efforts may fail despite good intentions.

Understanding curricula is a prerequisite for meaningful integration.

Levels of curriculum formation

- Levels:
 - **Supra:** International, comparative (e.g., European Higher Education Area)
 - **Macro:** System/society/nation/state (e.g., Universities Act, EMT)
 - **Meso:** Institution (e.g., university-specific curriculum)
 - **Micro:** Classroom (e.g., syllabi, assignments, assessments) -> syllabus
 - **Nano:** Individual/personal (e.g., student experience)

(Based on van den Akker 2010)

What is underneath the surface?

Official curriculum

- Learning outcomes
- Module descriptions
- Study regulations

Hidden curriculum

- Stakeholder expectations and values
- Technological developments
- Disciplinary norms
- Time pressure and workload realities

Image by MoteOo from Pixabay

Stakeholders shape curricula

Internal

- University leadership: funding parameters, admission rules
- Faculty: research priorities, teaching load constraints
- Educators: disciplinary norms and traditions, pedagogical and professional beliefs
- Students: employability, autonomy, flexibility

External

- EHEA: mobility, academic freedom, democratic participation
- Policy-makers: funding logics, access policies
- Professional associations: professional ethics, employability, market alignment
- EU training initiatives (EMT, EMCI): competence models, quality assurance, technology integration
- Other: e.g., CLARIN

(Lušicky & Iacono 2027)

Curricula are value-laden

- Curricula reflect what is considered important, legitimate, and desirable.
- Values may be:
 - **explicit** (acts, policies, competence frameworks) or
 - **implicit** (hidden curricula).
- Different values coexist and compete.

(Kearns 2012; Lušický & Iacono 2027)

Habitus: How hidden curricula become durable

- Educators and students internalise values (priorities) from official and hidden curricula:
 - What university teaching is for
 - Legitimacy of knowledge
 - What counts as ‘useful’
 - What counts as ‘real learning’
 - Value of research vs. practice
 - Technology optimism vs. scepticism
 - Disciplinary norms

(Lušicky & Iacono 2027)

Students' habitus: Example from past integration

- Selection criteria for LRs by Translations Studies students

(Lušicky & Wissik 2016)

(Mis)alignment of integration

- Expectations of students towards VLO

Desirable Metadata	
General Author(s) (of the texts) Year of publication Number of downloads Access (open, against payment, with registration) Time span Domain (e.g. environment, sport, medicine) Target group	Specific to Translation Studies Original language Translator(s) Mother tongue of the translator(s) Human translation or machine translation Information regarding the translation process Reliability of the text source

(Lušicky & Wissik 2016)

Reality check: What integration can – and cannot – do

Cannot:

- Create curricular space.
- Fix overload.
- Override institutional constraints.
- Address discipline-specific constraints, values and expectations.

Can:

- Make some hidden curricular expectations explicit.
- Shape habitus.
- Support selective entry points.

Curriculum literacy = Knowing where you can act

- At which curriculum formation level am I actually acting?
 - Supra: International, comparative
 - Macro: System/society/nation/state
 - Meso: Institution
 - Micro: Classroom
 - Nano: Individual/personal
- What is explicit, what is hidden? What should be explicit and official?
- What is fixed, what can be changed?

Vulnerable curriculum spider web

- Every chain is as strong as its weakest link.

Adapted, based on van den Akker, 2010

Analysis of values and expectations

- MA Translation
- Stakeholder documents, curricula, and educators and student perspectives

(Lušicky & Iacono 2027)

Integration at different levels of curriculum formation

- **Meso:**
 - 1) New additional study programme (MSc Multilingual Translations)
 - 2) Adapted official curricula (BA Transcultural Communication, MA Translation)
- **Micro:** Based on meso level
- **Nano:** Influence educators and students

Micro level: Classroom

- Alignment of aims and objectives vertically through the curriculum
- Identification of concrete courses and topics that support the rationale:
 - Exploratory search
 - FAIR
 - Metadata
 - Data management plan

UE Terminologiearbeit und Sprachressourcenmanagement Übersetzen

Ziele, Inhalte und Methode der Lehrveranstaltung

- Sprachressourcen; Typologie von Sprachressourcen (mit Schwerpunkt Korpora und Terminologiedatenbanken, Lexika, Thesauri, kontrollierte Vokabulare)
- Prinzipien des Sprachressourcenmanagements (FAIR), Metadaten
- Rechtliche und ethische Aspekte, Lizenzen, Wiederverwendung
- Relevante Kataloge, Repositorien, Initiativen (z.B. COPUS, CLARIN, ELG usw.)
- Relevante NLP-Ansätze
- Einsatz von Korpora in der translatorischen Praxis; praktische Arbeit mit Korpora (z.B. mit SketchEngine)
- Terminologiearbeit in der translatorischen Praxis (systematisch, punktuell, textbezogen, korpusgeleitet)
- Terminologiearbeit bedarfsorientiert zu initiieren, zu planen, umzusetzen und auf Qualität zu sichern
- Verwaltung von Terminologiedatenbanken, relevante Austauschformate
- Termextraktion
- Prinzipien der terminologischen Datenmodellierung
- Modellierung von Termdatenbanken für unterschiedliche Zwecke und Zielgruppen

(Lušicky 2026)

Final thoughts

- Curriculum is a:
 - multi-level system.
 - a system of constraints, negotiations, values and expectations.
- Integration succeeds when curriculum literacy guides integration.

References

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Thank you!

vesna.lusicky@univie.ac.at

Teaching with CLARIN: Where we were? What has been built? What still needs to happen?

**Iulianna van der Lek
CLARIN ERIC**

Where we were 7 years ago...

2019 CLARIN at Universities workshop:

- Between 2008 - 2020 CLARIN content was taught in 55 courses, 31 universities, 20 countries, reaching out to a total of 6000 students
- Mostly lecturer's initiative
- Across all study levels, but MA dominant
- **Disciplines:** mostly in Linguistics & Language, but also in DH, Language engineering, Cultural & media studies, Information and Computer Science
- **Coverage:** full courses, single session, few sessions
- **Modality:** lectures, exercises, assignments, online courses (rare)
- **Topics:** intro to RI, finding, accessing, reusing resources, depositing, metadata standards, legal & ethical issues, methods...

How CLARIN responded to 2019 recommendations

1. **Provide materials for teachers** -> CLARIN Learning Hub
2. **Support the exchange of teaching materials** -> Learning Resources Catalogue + SSH Open Marketplace, H2IOSC Platform and training offering more visible on the national consortia websites
3. **Provide teacher training** -> cafes, CLARIN101, workshops, webinars
4. **Support teacher exchange and collaboration** -> Trainers' Network, Mobility Grants, Training & Education track in annual conference CFP
5. **Learn from other RIs** -> Cross-infrastructure collaboration on training & capacity building in ATRIUM, ECHOES, OSCARS, OStrails, STARDAST etc.
6. **Technical development:** Add a facet to the VLO for resources & tools suited for teaching -> Add to Virtual Collections + specific metadata field in the learning resource catalogue

What we can further improve?

Preliminary findings from the 2026 Pre-workshop survey:

Aims:

- Understand how CLARIN resources and services are used in teaching
- Identify barriers to integration and assess needs
- Inform workshop program and future CLARIN training activities

Questions: (1) Demographics, (2) CLARIN integration in teaching, (3) use of other digital platforms & infrastructures, (4) (Re)Use of OER & FAIR practices

Respondents' Profile

- **23 respondents** representing **22** institutions across **18** EU countries
- **All respondents familiar with CLARIN**
- **Professional roles:** (assistant) professors, lecturers, researcher with teaching duties, *training officer in the CLARIN national consortium, programme coordinator with teaching duties, senior research librarian, RI specialist*
- **Teaching levels:** mostly at the MA, BA level, but als PhD and Postgraduate Certificate level

Subject Areas & Teaching Modality

- Similar to 2019, Linguistics and Language Studies, DH, LT/NL still dominant subject areas
- Hybrid teaching formats have become the norm

CLARIN in Teaching Practice: Awareness and Use of the Central Hub Services

- There is awareness but considerable variation in their pedagogical use
- Indicates a need for further support and training

CLARIN in Teaching Practice: Awareness and Use of the National Offerings

- High level of familiarity and integration of national CLARIN offerings in educational contexts
- Scope to support broader adoption

“I am teaching students...

Although a small sample, these results shows curriculum expansion across all study levels:

- Building FAIR resources
- Citation
- Depositing
- Legal and ethical issues
- ...

Teaching Data-Related Skills	BA	MA	PhD
Annotation	6	14	4
Building FAIR resources	2	8	4
Citing and referencing resources	5	10	2
Curating language resources		8	1
Depositing and sharing data	2	7	2
Exporting and reusing data	1	9	3
Legal and ethical issues	3	10	4
Searching & browsing collections	9	12	3
Standards & formats	1	4	4
Working with language data	4	11	4

Concrete use cases

- Rackevičienė, S. (2025, October 23). English-Lithuanian Language Resources for the Cybersecurity Domain. The 7th International Conference of Applied Linguistics "Languages and People", Vilnius University, Lithuania. Zenodo.
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16407468>

“I use the CLARIN tool named Korpusomat in Lexicography and Digital Tools classes in the Polish Philology field of study. As part of the course, students are required to compile their own language corpus: they upload a thematic collection of texts into the tool and present their corpus, discussing the functionalities of Korpusomat, including statistical analyses, frequency lists, keyword distributions, collocations, metadata plots, and sentiment analysis. They are also expected to demonstrate corpus querying using the tool's integrated search engine.”

Integration methods

- Unlike 2019, less full courses on CLARIN
- **New:** referring students to self-study tutorials and CLARIN videos

Teaching challenges

- Seem more structural than technical
- Need for more accessible teaching materials, institutional support and time-efficient ways for instructors to engage with CLARIN

Support needed

1. Ready-to-use datasets, suitable for teaching
2. Reusable slides for local adaptation
3. Ready-to-use teaching materials / sample lesson plans
4. Train-the-trainer session
5. Ready-to-use, student-oriented tutorials for self-learning
6. Technical support
7. Recorded tutorials
8. Other

Specific needs:

- Applied teaching examples, use of corpora in school-level pedagogy
- Teaching methods: sentiment analysis & MT using CLARIN resources
- Tools user guides, video tutorials
- Which resources are suitable to teach at which level
- Need for a reliable infrastructure and user support

Use of other digital platforms and infrastructures

Examples:

- Moodle, Canva, Blackboard, Brightspace
- Interactive Notebooks (Jupyter, Google Colab)
- Repositories & version control systems (GitHub)
- AI & ML platforms (Hugging Face, Kaggle)
- SketchEngine
- ...

Advantages & Limitations:

- + Accessibility & ease of use, no programming skills
- + Free computational resources (Google Colab)
- + No complex installation
- Limited flexibility of LMS
- Some platforms too challenging for students

FAIR practices in teaching materials development

- Awareness of FAIR-by-Design methodology, but not strictly following it
- Use of open & interoperable formats, metadata and PIDs, awareness of basic accessibility standards
- Half of the respondents share teaching / training materials outside their classroom, the other half shares them but only with specific colleagues within their institution
- **Platforms used:** Public repositories, CLARIN centres, cloud-based shared folders, YouTube, Open Moodle...
- **Challenges for sharing:** lack of time to format materials for public use, uncertainty about copyright/licences, no institutional incentive, technical difficulties using repositories

Re-use of open learning resources

- Awareness and (re)use of materials from existing platforms, e.g. Learning Hub, UPSKILLS, CLARIN YouTube video, SSH Open Marketplace, DARIAH Campus exist but
- There is considerable interest in learning more about available platforms and finding suitable materials for reuse in teaching
- **Barriers:** limited support for multilingual content and restrictions imposed by some platforms; some formats not supported by institutional LMS; licences and reuse conditions, unclear how to adapt and cite them

Future training needs that CLARIN should prioritise

- **Applied and practical topics** to help students connect tools and resources to specific research questions, e.g. data analysis for linguistic research, end-to-end workflows, data processing tasks
- **Training on AI and LLMs**, e.g. how to help students increase their LLM literacy, use them for fine-tuning, the impact of AI on academic writing
- **Specific topics:** terminology management, sentiment analysis, hate speech detection, multilingual alignment, statistics for the humanities, guidance on licencing, ethics & GDPR, standards, and data management
- **Materials tailored for different domains and user groups** (e.g. translators, language teachers, historians)
- Improvements for the Learning Hub

Lightning Talks: Strategies for Integrating CLARIN into University Curricula

14:00 - 15:00

Presentations

1. *How to Make CLARIN Visible Beyond One-Course Level by Communicating with University Authorities* by Jurgita Vaičenonienė
2. *Empowering Linguistics, Philology, and Educational Curricula with CLARIN: A Case Study at the University of the Aegean* by Katerina T. Frantzi
3. *Teaching and Learning Data Citation* by Mietta Lennes
4. *RDM for early career researchers: Adapting interdisciplinary teaching material to a linguistics context* by Helene N. Andreassen
5. *UPSKILLS Two Years on: Teaching about Language Resources & FAIR Data Principles with CLARIN* by Iulianna van der Lek

How to make CLARIN visible beyond one-course level by communicating with university authorities

Jurgita Vaičėnėnė

CLARIN - LT

Department of Lithuanian Studies, Vytautas Magnus
University, Kaunas, Lithuania

jurgita.vaicenoniene@vdu.lt

VMU changes in 2025: introducing “ourselves” to the newly elected VMU administration team

- Programme-level meeting (new chair): Sociolinguistics and Multilingualism
- Department-level meeting (new head): Department of Multilingual Studies
- Institute-level meeting (new chair): Institute of Exile Studies
- Faculty-level meeting (new dean): the Faculty of Humanities
- Vice-rector level meeting (new as well/planned in April)

“Case Study”

International Master in Sociolinguistics and Multilingualism
joint-degree study programme

About

- The International Master “Sociolinguistics and Multilingualism” (SoMu), jointly developed by four European universities in 2013, to provide students with a solid grounding in the social and academic aspects of sociolinguistics and multilingualism at a local, national, and international level.
- It is a joint degree programme offered by
 - Johannes Gutenberg-University Mainz (Germany) and
 - Vytautas Magnus University Kaunas (Lithuania) in cooperation
 - with Stockholm University (Sweden)
 - and the University of Tartu (Estonia)

Study Cycle

- **1st Semester: Kaunas**
- **2nd Semester: Mainz**
- **3rd Semester: Tartu or Stockholm**
- **4th Semester: university where the advisor of the M.A. thesis is employed.**
- Due to the built-in mobility that characterises the international joint degree, during the first three academic terms, students attend courses together with other multinational fellow students in the stimulating and inspiring atmosphere of the partner universities.
- At the end of the studies, the participants receive their diplomas from the two mother universities of the master programme: Vytautas Magnus University and Johannes Gutenberg University, Mainz.

Upcoming programme renewal in 2026

- New board and programme chair
- Plans to submit an application for an Erasmus Mundus Joint Master which aims to foster HEIs' excellence and worldwide internationalisation via Master level study programmes jointly delivered and jointly recognised in Europe and open to institutions in other countries of the world, increase the diversity and talent pool, enhance reputation and competitiveness on the global stage. ([Erasmus Mundus action](#))
- Chance for a consistent integration of CLARIN-related content in the updated curriculum.

SoMu board meeting (JGU, Mainz, January 19)

CLARIN in SoMu countries – access to data for all nodes:

- [CLARIN-LT](#) (Jurgita Vaičenonienė)

- [CLARIN-D](#) (Andreas Witt)

- [CLARIN-Estonia](#) (Joshua Wilbur)

- [Swe-CLARIN](#) (Sara Stymne)

Value to SoMu

SoMu focus areas:

1. Multilingualism
2. Migration
3. Language policy
4. Minority languages
5. Digital communication

CLARIN enables:

1. Cross-national corpora
2. Parliamentary debate datasets
3. Minority language resources
4. Comparable multilingual datasets
5. FAIR research practices

- CLARIN may strengthen methodological training
- Embeds SoMu in a European research infrastructure
- Aligns with Open Science and FAIR principles
- Creates cross-country comparative research opportunities
- Updates the curriculum with EU Open Science values

Integrating CLARIN content within the outline of particular courses (invited lecturers/ local NCs, trainers' network <...>)

- Introduction to CLARIN ERIC as a European RI.
- Hands-on use of the **Virtual Language Observatory (VLO)**.
- **Assignment:** Identify and evaluate corpora relevant to a SoMu topic (e.g., migration discourse, minority media, parliamentary debates).
- **FAIR/Research Data Management:** long-term data preservation, persistent identifiers, metadata standards, legal-ethical access regimes. Students prepare a mini Data Management Plan for their MA thesis; map their data to a CLARIN-compatible repository; reflect on reuse potential.
- **Use of CLARIN corpora and tools:**
 - Parliamentary debates (language policy analysis).
 - Minority language corpora (Baltic, Scandinavian, Germanic contexts).
- Students formulate **research questions**, extract sub-corpora, use corpus tools, etc.

A gradual build-up approach

- **1st semester: awareness of the infrastructure:**
 - Introductory CLARIN session.
 - VLO-based assignment (searching for relevant info/data).
- **2nd/3rd semesters: applied use of resources, tools, and other services:**
 - Corpus-based projects.
 - Comparative SoMu-country studies using CLARIN resources.
- **4th semester: contribution – (only) selected theses data?**
 - Thesis deposit in CLARIN-X repository.
 - Dataset documentation (DMPs submitted?)

Suggested workflow

- New curriculum is formed.
- Individual meetings with lecturers and CLARIN representatives organized to align CLARIN offers with learning outcomes/ course goals and co-design particular activities/ suggest particular tools, resources/ records/invited CLARIN trainers, etc.
- Pilots run (student feedback, examples of student work, lecturer reflections).

**Mapping Curriculum-> Aligning with Learning Outcomes -> Engaging Lecturers
-> Providing Ready-to-Use Materials -> Piloting in Selected Courses -> Scaling to
Programme Level**

What's next?

- The SoMu board members' opinions diverged...
- Possible follow-up (if invited):
 - Participation in new curriculum design
 - Participation in Erasmus Mundus proposal writing
- New student cohort if the programme is updated: autumn 2027.

Empowering Linguistics, Philology, and Educational Curricula with CLARIN: A Case Study at the University of the Aegean

Prof. Katerina T. Frantzi

Laboratory of Informatics

Department of Mediterranean Studies:

Archaeology, Linguistics, International Relations

How can CLARIN become
not just something we know as an
infrastructure,
but part of actual **teaching practice**,

something students **actively use** in
courses,
assignments,
thesis work, and
resource creation?

A model for integrating CLARIN into university teaching

Institutional context:

- courses involved
- examples of student participation
- completed resource that shows
the pedagogical value

Research and Teaching are Stronger Together

connect

- teaching
- thesis work
- resource creation

so that

students learn through
real CLARIN-related practice.

Their work can contribute to something reusable.

Strengths of the Approach

- hands-on research skills
- exposure to CLARIN resources and workflows
- contribution to reusable outputs

fresh perspectives and enthusiasm

Student Participation

- Begin with coursework
- Continue through MA assignments
- Develop into thesis work
- Contribute to resource building

CLARIN integration can be embedded
across different stages of the academic pathway.

Challenges

- time and supervision demands
- varying levels of student preparedness
- sustainability of outputs
- metadata and documentation workload

Department of Mediterranean Studies:
Archaeology, Linguistics, International Relations

School of Humanities
University of the Aegean

<https://dms.aegean.gr/en/>

Institutional Context

CLARIN-related integration takes place across several levels.

- Undergraduate Programme of Studies
- Two Postgraduate Programmes of the Department
- One Interdepartmental Postgraduate Programme

Undergraduate Programme: Division of Linguistics

- 7th semester: Corpus Processing (compulsory)
- 8th semester: Topics in Natural Language Processing (optional)

Corpus Processing – Course outline

- What is a corpus: definitions
- Types of corpora - corpus annotation
- Corpus-based and corpus-driven studies
- Applications of corpora in the Humanities and social sciences
- Corpus design and construction
- Greek corpora available on the web
- Corpus processing tools
- Corpus construction (practical session)
- **The National Infrastructure for Language Resources and Technologies: CLARIN:EL**

Topics in Natural Language Processing – Course Outline

- Corpus processing for linguistics, humanities, and social sciences
- Programming with Linux
- Extraction of word and collocation lists
- Language research questions using *grep* and regular expressions
- Formulating research questions in the humanities and social sciences
- National Infrastructures:
 - APOLLONIS
 - CLARIN:EL
 - DARIAH-GR

Postgraduate Programmes (MA)

1. **Ancient Theatre: Educational & Literary Approaches**
2. **Archaeology of the Eastern Mediterranean**
3. **Analysis and Teaching of First and Second/Foreign Language**

(Interdepartmental with the Department of Primary Education)

Postgraduate Programmes - Courses

Ancient Theatre: Educational & Literary Approaches

Computational Processing of the Language of Ancient Drama (2nd semester)

Archaeology of the Eastern Mediterranean

Digital Language Resources for Ancient Studies (2nd semester)

Analysis and Teaching of First and Second/Foreign Language

Corpora in Language Teaching (2nd semester)

Computational Processing of the Language of Ancient Drama – Course outline

Corpora: definitions, corpus-based studies, and corpus-driven studies

Types of corpora, corpus annotation, and frequency normalization

Applications of corpora in the humanities, philology, and education

Ancient drama corpora available on the web

Design and construction of an ancient drama corpus

Corpus processing tools

Processing ancient drama: educational applications

Processing ancient drama: research applications

The *Greek Dramaturgy Corpus* of the National Infrastructure for Language Resources and Technologies (CLARIN:EL)

Digital Language Resources for Ancient Studies – Course outline

Digital Language Resources (DLR): contribution to the humanities and ancient studies

Types of DLRs

Digital language resources for ancient studies available on the web

Ready-to-use tools for processing DLRs in ancient studies

Applications of DLRs to research questions in ancient studies

Applications of DLRs to educational practices in ancient studies

National Infrastructures: APOLLONIS, CLARIN:EL, DARIAH-GR

Corpora in Language Teaching – Course outline

Corpus: Definition, historical background, types, and annotation

Frequency normalization

Corpus-based and corpus-driven approaches to language study and teaching

Corpus design and construction for language teaching purposes

Freely available online Greek corpora

Freely available online corpus processing tools

Learner corpora

The National Infrastructure for Language Resources and Technologies: CLARIN:EL

Special Topics: applications of corpora in the study and teaching of first and second/foreign languages

Completed Project: Language Resource “Ancient Greek Dramaturgy”

Developed within the framework of the course:

Computational Processing of the Language of Ancient Drama

MA: Ancient Theatre: Educational & Literary Approaches

From the Classical era (472 BC), with the earliest tragedy *Persians* by Aeschylus to the Hellenistic era (316 BC), and the latest surviving play, *Dyskolos*

Ancient Greek Dramaturgy (2021). Version 1.0.0 (automatically assigned). [Dataset (Text corpus)].

CLARIN:EL. <http://hdl.handle.net/11500/CLARIN-EL-0000-0000-6113-D>

University of the Aegean Repository

Language Resource “Ancient Greek Dramaturgy”

- the tragedies of the three great classical playwrights: **Aeschylus**, **Sophocles**, **Euripides**, including the only surviving satyr play, *Cyclops* by Euripides
- all the fully preserved comedies of **Aristophanes**
- the only satisfactorily preserved comedy of the Hellenistic period, *Dyskolos* by Menander
- the fragment of *Rhesus*

45 works

1.34 million words

- ancient text
- monotonic text
- translated text

Students do not only collect texts;

they learn

documentation and
metadata practices

compatible with

infrastructure-based reuse

metadata

- title
- file name
- genre (comedy, tragedy, satyr play)
- source
- translators of the Modern Greek texts
- type of translation (verse or prose)
- word count of each file
- chronology
- number of characters
- presence of a Chorus / presence of a double Chorus

Ongoing Projects

Corpus of Greek Diaspora Textbooks

Annotating the Ancient Greek Dramaturgy Corpus

Learner Corpus: collection and organisation of primary school and kindergarten learners' discourse

Learner Corpus: collection and organisation of learners' discourse in Greek as a second/foreign language

- Modern Greek Translations of Ancient Drama: “Persians”, “Oedipus Tyrannus”, “Bacchae”: A Comparative Study of the Use of Content Words
- *Man and Woman* in the Comedies of Aristophanes: *Lysistrata*, *Thesmophoriazusae*, *Ecclesiazusae*: A Corpus-Based Study Using the National Infrastructure for Language Resources and Technologies CLARIN:EL
- Divine Madness in Euripides’ *Bacchae* and *Hippolytus*: A Comparative Corpus-Based Study Using the National Infrastructure for Language Resources and Technologies CLARIN:EL
- The Language of Emotions in Sophocles: A Corpus-Based Study Using the National Infrastructure for Language Resources and Technologies CLARIN:EL
- *Woman* in Aeschylus and Sophocles: A Corpus-Based Study Using the National Infrastructure for Language Resources and Technologies CLARIN:EL

- *Woman* in Euripides: A Corpus-Based Study Using the National Infrastructure for Language Resources and Technologies CLARIN:EL
- Representations of Divine Justice in Aeschylean Tragedy: A Philological and Linguistic Analysis
- Euripides: Misogynist or Philogynist? A Corpus-Based Study Using the National Infrastructure for Language Resources and Technologies CLARIN:EL
- A Study of the Language of Rhetoric in Ancient Tragedy Using Corpus-Based Methodology
- The Use and Function of Dialects in Ancient Greek Tragedy

Sample Publications and Announcements Related to Master's Theses Using CLARIN:EL

Kalamara, P. S., & Frantzi, K. T. (2023). *Euripides and divine madness in the Bacchae and Hippolytus. Kathedra of Byzantine and Modern Greek Studies*, 16(3), 121–139. (in Greek)

Cheimaras, G., & Frantzi, K. T. (2024). *The digital language resource of Ancient Greek philosophy. 2nd International Scientific Conference “Teaching Greek Language: Methods, Innovations, Prospects”*, Moscow, hybrid format, 1–3 October 2024. (in Greek)

Panoliaskou, G., & Frantzi, K. T. (2025). *References to “Woman” in the tragedies of Euripides: A corpus-based study. 8th International Conference of Greek Studies in Memory of the Distinguished Colleague Irina Kovaleva*, hybrid format, Moscow, 15–17 April 2025. (in Greek)

Frantzi, K. T., & Kyprianidi, I. (2026). *Teaching English as a foreign language in primary school: A pilot corpus of fifth- and sixth-grade pupils*. In a volume dedicated to Emerita Professor Maria Skourtou, University of the Aegean. (in Greek)

Frantzi, K. T., & Kyprianidi, I. (2026, forthcoming). *A pilot corpus of fifth- and sixth-grade primary school pupils for teaching German as a foreign language*. In *Proceedings of the 11th International Conference of the Institute of Humanities and Social Sciences (IAKE), Creative Communities: Participation and Initiative in Institutional Collective Bodies: Society, Education, Political Deliberation*, hybrid format, Heraklion, Crete, 8–11 May 2025. (in Greek)

Conclusions

- CLARIN is not only a research infrastructure.
- It can be integrated into existing courses, beyond standalone training.
- Students learn analysis, but also documentation, metadata, and sharing practices.
- It connects coursework with thesis work and reusable outputs.
- Students move from using resources to understanding how resources are created, documented, shared, and reused.

CLARIN is not only a research infrastructure.
It can function as a meaningful pedagogical framework.

Thank you!

Teaching and Learning Data Citation

Mietta Lennes

University of Helsinki / FIN-CLARIN

Why are data citations necessary?

- Replicability of scientific research (FAIR principles)
 - declaration of the source as provenance information
- Attribution
 - recognition of scientific merit (good practice)
 - declaration of the source as required by the license
- (For measuring impact?)

Why teach (data) citation practices?

- Learning how to cite previous research (publications) and to use bibliographic references is still a fundamental part of getting a university degree.
- Data citation practices are not yet as well-established, but data reuse is becoming more and more popular.

Is it easy to cite data?

- Many repositories already provide citation instructions that are generated automatically from the resource metadata. (*But this is not always the case.*)
- If a citation instruction is not offered, all the pieces of information for citing a data set should at least be accessible in the public metadata record. (*But this is not always the case.*)

Creators (Authors)

Publication Year

Title and Version

Kinnunen, T., Hautamäki, R. G., Sahidullah, M., Hautamäki, V., Werner, S., & Bentz, M. (2019). Corpus of Age-related Voice Disguise (AVOID) [data set]. Kielipankki. <http://urn.fi/urn:nbn:fi:lb-2018060621>

Resource Type

Publisher

Persistent Identifier (PID)

Creators (authors)

- Ordered list of the persons and/or the organizations responsible for collecting and organizing the resource
- Not to be confused with the role of the 'publisher' or with the original authors of the individual documents
- May also be different from the 'right holders'
- The creators of several corpora/subcorpora should preferably not be concatenated into one reference item, not even if the resources are used together as one set.

Publication year

- The first availability date of this resource by this publisher
(The publication time of the "original" resource may be difficult to specify, especially for derived or combined resources.)

Title and version

- The title should be used systematically in the same format in which it is provided in the resource metadata
- The main title can be supplemented with extensions, e.g.,
 - the version of the resource: “version 1.1”, “version 2021-05-17”,
 - a description of the available variant that was used: "download", "Korp" (concordancer)

Publisher

- The publisher is the entity who technically maintains the deposited data and its metadata (and spends some resources on this).
 - e.g., Kielipankki (the Language Bank of Finland), LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ, Zenodo, ...
 - cf. the publisher of a book

Persistent identifier (PID)

- A PID of a resource/data set can be, e.g., a DOI, a Handle, or a URN.
- In case the PID and the resource title have been used consistently in citations, the use of the resource can be tracked down via, e.g., Google Scholar searches.
- However, even PIDs may be broken unless they are curated!

... To be further developed:

- Citing continuously **accumulating resources**
 - Add the retrieval date and time, if appropriate
- References to individual **documents/locations within a data set**
 - Provide the citation of the entire data set, specify the partial content in the text of your publication.
- References to **terms within a terminology resource**, developed by the research community? Cf. *The Helsinki Term Bank for the Arts and Sciences*, <https://tieteentermipankki.fi>

CLARIN can promote data citation

- Matthiesen, M. and Lenardič, J. (2025). *CLARIN Citation Guidelines*. <https://doi.org/10.34733/doc-189>
- CLARIN needs to work towards providing consistent citation instructions for all datasets on VLO (technical efforts for common CMDI components?)
- **Meanwhile**, students need to learn how they can gather the details required to cite data.
- Could CLARIN offer a page with citation examples?

RDM for early career researchers: Adapting interdisciplinary teaching material to a linguistics context

Helene N. Andreassen

UiT The Arctic University of Norway

Repositories our 220 respondents know

220 respondents
All career stages

([LDIG RDA](#) survey
results to be published)

Background data: Challenges to archiving data

220 respondents
All career stages

([LDIG RDA](#) survey results to be published)

Additional challenges to archiving reported

- Constantly changing infrastructure & not knowing where to turn for help
- GDPR & Indigenous Data Sovereignty
- IRB/Ethics boards who do not understand why data should be archived as openly as possible
- Protectionist collaborators and colleagues

([LDIG RDA](#) survey results to be published)

Training received vs. wanted

Low uptake of archiving practices: Not necessarily a question of availability of services

- Lack of communication & Misalignment of services?
- Lack of incentives & Lack of time?

- Problem of identifying oneself in the training offered?
The one size does perhaps not fit all → any training must meet the needs across sub-disciplines and data types → must feel relevant and applicable to current research projects.

To mitigate challenges

- Organisation of training **locally** (the department is the “formative social space where the values of a disciplinary culture are acquired”, cf. Dobrin, 2025)
- **Collaboration** between research communities and RDM expertise
- Reuse (and adjustment) of **existing educational material**

Illustration: MostPhotos

The DocEnhance Data Stewardship course

Andreassen, H. N. et al.
(2025). *DocEnhance Data Stewardship Course: Executive summary and teacher guide*. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17121474>

- Developed as part of the EU-funded project DocEnhance (2020-2022) → transferable skills and employability for ECRs
- Covers the entire research data management life cycle.
- Designed to meet the needs of PhD candidates across all disciplines and data types.
- Combines theoretical knowledge with reflections around own projects, practical exercises and real-world applications.

DocEnhance

The three modules of Data Stewardship

- **Module 1:** Online MOOC focusing on theory and best practices in research data management.
- **Module 2:** Week-long-ish, in-person workshop with collaborative activities.
- **Module 3:** Practical application of knowledge through placements with local businesses or public sector employers.

- **Interdisciplinary and practical focus:**
Encourages collaboration and equips participants with skills directly applicable to their research and future careers.

Open and flexible teaching material

- One main purpose of Data Stewardship: **Reuse in new contexts**
- All material **openly available** with a CC-BY license.
- **Flexible** and user-friendly with extensive teacher guides; allows adjustment to fit with target group (career stage, level of knowledge, discipline, data type, time available, preferences, ...)
- Regularly **updated** by the UiT editorial team.

Data Stewardship reused (also by our community?)

- Course used by several European universities (PhD level)
- Course material adapted by EUGLOH (European University Alliance for Global Health)

- 1 possible way forward for linguistics to consider: **Collaboration** (CLARIN, LDIG, DS developers, interested institutions, ...) on developing/testing a **discipline-specific version** (e.g. starting with Module 2), perhaps focussing on ECRs, and taking into account the **diversity** of data types, available tools & resources in CLARIN, and challenges across sub-disciplines.

Thanks for your attention!

My contact information

helene.n.andreassen@uit.no

To access the course material

<https://courses.docenhance.eu/>

To join LDIG

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/linguistics-data-ig/activity/>

UPSKILLS Two Years on: Teaching about Language Resources & FAIR Data Principles with CLARIN

Iulianna van der Lek, CLARIN ERIC

Maja Miličević Petrovic, UNIBO, FORLI based on

UPSKILLS two years on: Teaching about language resources and FAIR data principles with CLARIN

Iulianna van der Lek, Maja Miličević Petrovic, Silvia Bernardini, Adriano Ferraresi, Olga Arsić

(Upcoming CLARIN2025 Post-Proceedings)

It all started with UPSKILLS ...

UPgrading the SKills of Linguistics and Language Students,
Erasmus+ strategic partnership, 2020-2023.

It all started with UPSKILLS ...

UPgrading the SKills of Linguistics and Language Studies
Erasmus+ strategic partnership, 2020-2023!

Language data and project specialist

- knowledge, skills and competences -

One of CLARIN's
roles was to raise
awareness of
Open Science and
FAIR data
principles

DISCIPLINARY

- Knowledge of specific languages
- Ability to conduct linguistic analysis
- Translation, interpreting, post-editing, localisation

(INTER)CULTURAL

- Awareness of specific cultural contexts and cultural differences
- Cultural agility

TRANSVERSAL

- Creative and innovative thinking
- Problem-solving skills
- Presentation skills
- Writing for different audiences

TECHNICAL

- Understanding and use of language technologies and resources
- Understanding of computational linguistics / NLP
- Knowledge of a programming language

DATA-ORIENTED

- Ability to collect, manage, curate, analyse language data
- Knowledge of statistics
- Familiarity with data standards

RESEARCH-ORIENTED

- Knowledge of research design
- Analytical, logical and hypothetical thinking
- Accessing and processing information critically

ORGANISATIONAL

- Entrepreneurship
- Project management
- Quality control
- Planning
- Teamwork

Illustration by Freepik Storyset, <https://storyset.com/data>

UPSKILLS learning content (2023)

A Glimpse into Language Data Science

Analytical Thinking and Problem Solving

Automatic Speech Recognition and Forced Alignment

Collecting Language Data from Human Participants

First Steps into Scientific Research

Introduction to Language Data: Standards and Repositories

Project Management

Start Programming with Python in 10 Steps

Processing Texts and Corpora

The Essence of Machine Learning for Linguists in Tech

Upskilling your "Introduction to Language variation" course

Introduction to Language data Standards & Repositories

Two years later...

Department of Interpreting and Translation, UNIBO's Forlì campus

Several UPSKILLS-related curricular components:

BA Languages & Technologies for Intercultural Communication

- Computational Thinking
- Text Processing
- Researching Language

MA Specialized Translation - Translation & Technology

- Profession-Based Research
- Corpus Linguistics
- Natural Language Processing
- Language Data Analysis

Integrating OS and FAIR skills

CLARIN guest lectures in March 2025:

- Introduction to CLARIN [BA]
- Overview of the FAIR data principles [BA]
- Basic FAIR assessment of published corpora [BA/MA]
- Corpus depositing workflow in CLARIN-IT's repository [BA/MA]
- Specific issues in corpus data depositing [meetings, PhD & staff]

Recommendations & next steps

- Topics related to language resources, FAIR Principles and OS can be introduced in any language & linguistics-related programme.
- Possible next steps:
 - help teachers map the proposed LOs to their curriculum/classroom goals;
 - use this framework to design learning paths linking to existing learning resources from the Learning Resources Catalogue
- Our proposal is open for community contributions:

Topic	Learning objectives		
	BA	MA	PhD
Open Science and FAIR Data Principles	Recognise	Use	Apply
Research Infrastructures and Data Repositories			
Finding and (Re)Using Language Resources	Define	Assess	Solve
Analyzing Language Resources			
Building and Managing Language Resources	Explain	Analyze	Contribute
Sharing and Archiving Language Resources			

<https://tinyurl.com/3u8c72s>

Day 1 - Part 2

- **15:00 - 15:30 Coffee Break**
- **15:30 - 16:30 Breakout Session 1 (all):**
 - Best Practice Exchange: Needs, Barriers and Solutions
- **16:30 - 17:15 Plenary reporting (all)**
- **17:15 - 17:30 Conclusions of the 1st Day and Next Steps**
- **19:00 Dinner**
 - Restaurant De Zakkendrager
Zakkendragerssteeg 26, 3511 AA Utrecht

Breakout Session 1

Group Name & Moderators	Participants	Shared Notes/ Worksheets
<p>Group 1 - Language Technology, NLP, Speech, Computer & Information Sciences</p> <p>Moderator: Petya Osenova (confirmed)</p>	<p>Petya, Slavko Žitnik, Vincent Vandeghinste, Florian Kunneman, Mietta Lennes, Christoph Draxler, Barbara</p>	<p>Notes</p>
<p>Group 2 - Linguistics & Language Studies, Corpus Linguistics</p> <p>Moderator: Therese Lindström Tiedemann (confirmed)</p>	<p>Therese Lindström Tiedemann, Ilze Auziņa, Kinga Wąsińska, Katerina Frantzi, Michal Křen, Darja, Maarja-Liisa Pilvik</p>	<p>Notes</p>
<p>Group 3 - Translation & Interpreting Studies, Terminology, Lexicography</p> <p>Moderator: Vesna Lusicky (confirmed)</p>	<p>Vesna, Jurgita Vaičenonienė, Sigita Rackevičienė, Daša Farkaš</p>	<p>Notes</p>
<p>Group 4 - Data stewardship</p> <p>Moderator: Helene N. Andreassen (confirmed)</p>	<p>Helene N. Andreassen, Giulia Pedonese, Iulianna, Henk, Thalassia</p>	<p>Notes</p>
<p>Group 5 - DH, Humanities, Literary Studies, Media Studies</p> <p>Moderator: Valeria Quochi (confirmed)</p>	<p>Valeria Quochi, Megan Bushnell, Federico Boschetti, Stefán Ólafsson, Christian Olesen, Steven</p>	<p>Notes</p>

Plenary Reporting & Discussion (All)

16:30 - 17:15

Each breakout group will present (10 min per group, incl. Q&Q):

- Its most urgent teaching challenge and the most feasible solution
- One concrete resource or module concept to be developed
- One recommendation for CLARIN central hub and/or national consortia, their programme coordinator, or curriculum designers

Plenary Reporting

Group Name & Moderators	Participants
Group 1 - Language Technology, NLP, Speech, Computer & Information Sciences Moderator: Petya Osenova?	Petya, Slavko Žitnik, Vincent Vandeghinste, Florian Kunneman, Mietta Lennes, Christoph Draxler, Barbara
Group 2 - Linguistics & Language Studies, Corpus Linguistics Moderator: Therese Lindström Tiedemann	Therese Lindström Tiedemann, Ilze Auziņa, Kinga Wąsińska, Katerina Frantz, Michal KŘEN, Darja
Group 3 - Translation & Interpreting Studies, Terminology, Lexicography Moderator: Vesna Lusicky?	Vesna, Jurgita Vaičenonienė Sigita Rackevičienė, Maarja-Liisa Pilvik, Daša Farkaš
Group 4 - Data stewardship Moderator: Helene N. Andreassen?	Helene N. Andreassen, Giulia Pedonese, Iulianna, Henk, Thalassia
Group 5 - DH, Humanities, Literary Studies, Media Studies Moderator: Valeria Quochi?	Valeria Quochi, Megan Bushnell, Federico Boschetti, Stefán Ólafsson, Christian Olesen

Conclusions of the 1st Day and Next Steps

17:15 - 17:30

Conclusions Day 1

- [CLARIN Zenodo community](#) can be used to share materials and presentation in different languages
- Multilinguality:
 - Localization of existing materials in collaboration with the students in Translation classes
 - Localization of the CLARIN website in other languages
- CLARIN Forum can be used more to exchange examples when resources are not mature enough for Zenodo
- Embed multilinguality in the CLARIN
- Collaboration with the K-centres to organise workshop
- Create concrete example (use cases) based on real-world problems
- Teachers can use Switchboard to identify tools suited for teaching
- Build modular training resources

Conclusions Day 1

- Students are the way to integrate CLARIN in Universities (Thesis, Data Citations, repositories)
- Collaboration is necessary:
 - Consortia need to collaborate to further develop existing materials or make them relevant for specific disciplines
 - Teachers are not the main entry point. Also important to collaborate with university, libraries, research data management, DH centres
 - Set up a data stewardship network with expertise in language data
- Ensure that the CLARIN repositories are registered in [re3data.registry](https://re3data.org/) and FAIRsSharing as they are promoted in existing courses